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AUTHORS

Aysen Fenercioglu
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2965-6102>

AFFILIATIONS

Istanbul University
Cerrahpaşa Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Istanbul, Turkey

ABSTRACT

With the increasing elderly population, the number of patients with chronic conditions and the scope of home care services are expanding. This development is also affecting the way home care services are delivered and increasing the role of technology-driven approaches.

Telemedicine, as a concept, refers to applications used both among healthcare professionals and between the healthcare system and patients. It is a broad term that encompasses a range of technologies, from digital radiography and telephone consultations to video conferencing and remote surgery.

Telehealth, on the other hand, is a remotely accessible network used by all healthcare professionals for the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases, as well as the continuous improvement of healthcare services between citizens and healthcare personnel.

In home healthcare services, artificial intelligence is widely used in electronic health records, mobile health, telehealth, remote patient monitoring, and patient tracking sensors. Today, it is particularly utilized in online service documentation, medication safety applications, and the recording and monitoring of patient safety indicators.

Wearable technologies are among the recent innovations in home healthcare services. These include sensor-equipped devices such as smart bracelets, watches, shirts, and badges that collect a person's data through sensors and provide personalized feedback.

KEYWORDS

Home healthcare, telemedicine, artificial intelligence, wearable technology, elderly care, remote monitoring

INTRODUCTION

For home healthcare services to be effective and efficient, they must continuously adapt to changes and integrate technological advancements into service delivery. With the increase in the elderly population, the number of patients with chronic illnesses is also rising, and the scope of home care services is expanding. These changes are influencing how care is delivered at home and increasing the role of technology-oriented approaches (Merih, Ertürk, Yemenici & Satman, 2021).

Today, access to healthcare services is a significant concern. Therefore, telehealth applications can facilitate the regular monitoring of elderly individuals and patients with chronic conditions who face challenges in accessing healthcare services. Additionally, such applications may contribute to reducing healthcare expenditures (Heinz et al., 2012; Hersh et al., 2001)

DEFINITION

Telemedicine and telehealth are closely related concepts. Telemedicine refers to practices used both between healthcare professionals and between the healthcare system and patients. It is a broad term encompassing a range of technologies—from digital radiology and phone consultations to video conferencing and remote surgery. In other words, it involves the use of telecommunication technologies to deliver medical care or services (Dilbaz, Kaplanoglu & Kaya, 2020).

Telehealth, on the other hand, is a remote-access network used by all healthcare professionals to diagnose, treat, and prevent diseases, as well as to continuously improve healthcare services, by facilitating

communication between citizens and healthcare personnel (Dilbaz, Kaplanoğlu & Kaya, 2020). Various terminologies can be encountered in the field of telehealth, including e-Health and m-Health.

The World Health Organization defined telehealth in 2010 as: “The delivery of healthcare services, where distance is a critical factor, by all healthcare professionals using information and communication technologies for the exchange of valid information for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and for the continuing education of healthcare providers, all in the interests of advancing the health of individuals and their communities.” (World Health Organization [WHO], 2010)

As this definition suggests, telehealth serves as an umbrella term encompassing many remote access services, including telemedicine. These remote access applications include video conferencing, secure messaging, internet-based computer and phone applications. In essence, the scope ranges from voice calls and text messaging to wearable technologies and remote patient monitoring (telemonitoring) (Figure 1). The most significant disadvantage of telehealth is the lack of opportunity for immediate intervention in acute patient situations.

TELEHEALTH IN HOME HEALTHCARE

According to a study investigating the most common conditions for which telehealth is used, this service is applied in 45% of diabetes cases, 15% of hypertension (HT), 10% of depression, 9% of heart failure, 6% of dementia, and 2% of COPD/asthma and kidney failure cases (Wainwright & Wootton, 2003).

When examining global examples of telehealth use, it has been observed that compared to traditional care, telephone support from nurses and home telemonitoring have contributed to reduced hospitalization rates (Jerant et al., 2007). Studies have shown that patients in the telemonitoring group exhibited significantly improved self-care behaviors compared to those receiving home visits (Benatar et al., 2003; Chaudhry, Mattera, Spertus & Krumholz, 2007).

According to the results of a study conducted by Cleland et al. (2005), patients who received home telemonitoring or nurse telephone support had higher survival rates compared to those who received traditional care. Furthermore, patients in the telemonitoring group had a 26% reduction in the number of days spent in the hospital compared to those who received only telephone support (Cleland et al., 2005).

Telehealth can also be applied in the field of preventive medicine, referred to as tele-preventive medicine. For example, studies have shown that telehealth use in smoking cessation counseling yields results similar to those achieved through face-to-face interaction. The use of telehealth for promoting healthy eating habits has also been found to be beneficial (Hersh et al., 2001). In individuals with diabetes, telehealth services are utilized to improve access to healthcare and enhance quality of life.

TECHNOLOGY TRENDS IN HOME HEALTHCARE

The importance of current technology trends -such as big data, artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), precision health, the Internet of Things (IoT), and wearable technologies- is increasing in home healthcare services (Merih, Ertürk, Yemenici & Satman, 2021).

Big Data: Big data refers to larger and more complex datasets obtained particularly from new data sources. In healthcare, big data includes information embedded in emerging technologies such as AI, VR, AR, precision medicine, and the Internet of Things. These datasets are valuable not only for diagnosing, treating, and monitoring diseases but also for generating legal records and serving as data sources for scientific research (Gonzalez Jimenez, 2011).

Internet of Things (IoT): IoT refers to technologies involving embedded devices, sensors, and detection networks in objects/devices, supported by advanced internet protocols. In home healthcare, IoT applications include mobile health services, remote patient care, preventive systems, diagnostics, treatment, and patient monitoring systems. These involve physiological sensors used for remote monitoring, medication adherence, tracking medical equipment, and preventing medical errors (such as incorrect drug/dose/time/procedure). Wireless body area networks (WBANs), which collect biological signals from the human body—such as ECG, oximeter, Holter monitor, and blood glucose measurements—are also included in this category (Bini, 2018).

Artificial Intelligence (AI): AI involves replicating human cognitive functions through computers and enabling machines to learn to a certain degree. The most well-known AI methods include expert systems, fuzzy logic, artificial neural networks (ANNs), and genetic algorithms.

In home healthcare, AI is widely used in electronic health records, mobile health, telehealth, remote monitoring, and patient tracking sensors. Today, it plays a key role in online service documentation, medication safety applications, and the recording and tracking of patient safety indicators. AI-powered decision-support systems also help prevent medical errors (Whende, 2020).

AI-supported robots are employed in various areas, including drug testing and production, logistics, patient treatment, and care. Additionally, robots increasingly assist healthcare professionals in everyday tasks such as dressing, bathing, patient transport, monitoring, rehabilitation, and providing emotional support (Gonzalez Jimenez, 2011; Whende, 2020).

Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality: Virtual reality creates a simulated environment where individuals feel as though they are physically present in a different setting. It is often defined as an alternative world in which users can move, supported by fiber optic data, gloves, and video goggles. VR systems consist of computers, goggles, headphones, and motion-sensing equipment. VR is used to create computer-based, three-dimensional, immersive environments.

Augmented reality (AR), in contrast, overlays virtual elements onto real-world settings. VR and AR are used in surgical training, other healthcare professional education, patient education, rehabilitation, and exercise programs (Whende, 2020).

Precision Health: Precision health refers to the development of diagnostic, treatment, and prevention tools tailored to individuals with similar genetic, environmental, and lifestyle characteristics, rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. Also known as personalized medicine, it considers individual variability in genes, environment, and lifestyle when addressing diseases. It utilizes electronic health records, genetic testing, big data analytics, and supercomputers. Precision medicine is used especially in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of cancer, neurodegenerative disorders, and rare genetic conditions (König et al., 2017).

Wearable Technologies: Wearable technologies are systems that collect individual data via sensors and provide personalized feedback. These devices include sensor-equipped smart bracelets, watches, shirts, and badges that can monitor parameters like blood pressure and oxygen saturation.

They are particularly useful in the home care of patients with cardiovascular diseases. These devices also support mood and sleep disorder monitoring, elderly care, and transmitting sleep data to healthcare professionals when needed (Stavropoulos et al., 2020).

There have been major advancements in wearable systems such as sensor-embedded garments, airbag vests to prevent fall-related injuries, and balance control systems. Monitoring systems integrated with smart clothing at home provide a safe environment and help detect health-deteriorating activity or routine changes through data analysis (Merih, Ertürk, Yemenici & Satman, 2021).

Smartwatches, bracelets, and necklaces are used to prevent wandering in elderly and dementia patients. Smart bracelets, watches, and badges help detect fall risks. Wearable devices like bands and watches capable of ECG monitoring, heart rate tracking, and oxygen saturation measurement are used in cardiovascular disease management. Specialized utensils such as spoons and forks are designed for individuals with Parkinson's tremors to support independent eating.

Bone-conduction headphones and sensor-equipped devices are used for hearing impairments. Airbag vests are employed to prevent pressure sores and back injuries. Smart wristbands that assist in dietary monitoring can be used in obesity management. Breath-analyzing devices are available for respiratory conditions.

Wearable support systems are helpful for individuals with balance disorders. Devices capable of measuring glucose and transmitting data to mobile applications are used in diabetes care. Smart socks that enable early detection of diabetic foot ulcers are another innovative example (Merih, Ertürk, Yemenici & Satman, 2021; Stavropoulos et al., 2020; Whende, 2020).

FACTORS THAT MAY INFLUENCE THE COURSE AND SUCCESS OF TELEHEALTH APPLICATIONS (Aslan, 2021)

1. The nature of the disease/condition
2. The stage of the disease/condition
3. Whether there are any barriers to accessing the service (e.g., physical, economic, technical)
4. Ethical boundaries related to the service process
5. The legal framework of the service
6. Sustainability of the service
7. Integration of the service with existing care models
8. User acceptability of the service
9. Satisfaction with the service
10. Existence of systems to prevent disruptions in service delivery
11. Measures to ensure that service models do not lead to any form of discrimination
12. Availability of qualified personnel to provide the service
13. Competency of the service providers

LIMITATIONS OF TELEMEDICINE APPLICATIONS (Aslan, 2021)

1. The effectiveness of telemedicine applications depends not only on computer availability but also on the presence of appropriate software.
2. There is a need for more research on cost–benefit analyses.
3. Telemedicine does not fully replace face-to-face physician–patient communication.
4. Communication and steps like physical examination may be interrupted.
5. Inequities in access to telemedicine are a significant drawback.
6. Elderly individuals may face challenges in accessing telemedicine services.
7. Technical issues may cause disruptions in telemedicine services.
8. Proper patient selection is crucial for successful telemedicine implementation.
9. Not all patients may prefer or accept telemedicine services.
10. Adjusting medication doses based on body composition may be problematic or error-prone in telemedicine settings.
11. Telemedicine may not be appropriate or applicable for all clinical conditions.
12. Concerns may arise regarding patient privacy and data protection.
13. There may be challenges related to the boundaries of medical responsibility. Particularly, cross-border telemedicine services may require clear regulatory frameworks.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Aysen Fenercioglu

Istanbul University

Cerrahpaşa Faculty of Medicine

Department of Family Medicine

Istanbul, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2965-6102>

aysenfenerci@hotmail.com